

ADOLESCENCE IS A CRISIS OF MENTAL DEVELOPMENT**Zarema Ismoilovna Setsalieva**

Kokan State Pedagogical Institute Head of the Methodological Department of Primary Education.

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Abstract. In the article by the Soviet psychologist L.S. Based on the ideas of Vygotsky, analyzes were made. Adolescence is divided into two periods - the period of younger adolescence and the period of older adolescence.

Keywords: adolescence, mental development, crisis, education, psychology, society, socio-political, synthesis, analysis.

ПОДРОСТКОВЫЙ ВОЗРАСТ - КРИЗИС ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. В статье советского психолога Л.С. на основе идей Выготского проведен анализ. Подростковый возраст делится на два периода — период младшей юности и период старшей юности.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, психическое развитие, кризис, воспитание, психология, общество, социально-политический, синтез, анализ.

INTRODUCTION

We must always remember that the promising young generation of our country depends on how it is brought up, what spiritual qualities it will grow up with, how active our children are in life, how much they serve higher goals and good. The spiritual world of our children is rounded, they are spiritually and morally mature, physically we must always take care and fight for their health. The future begins today. If education is neglected now, the future will be lost. Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and other truly human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Adolescence is characterized by such psychological manifestations as "transitional period", "crisis period", "difficult period". Because in the behavior of teenagers of this age there are also cases of mental explosion due to the fact that they could not find their place in alternative, new conditions. At one time, L.S. Vygotsky called such a situation "crisis of mental development". Lev Semenovich Vygotsky (1896-1934) - Soviet psychologist, who carried out major scientific works in the field of pedagogy and psychology. According to his theory, in adolescence there are several "crises" that are important in mental development. These crises are natural stages of mental development and represent special periods of the inner world of each person and relationships with society.

Vygotsky's views on the crisis of mental development:

1. Highly structured social relations. In his socio-political theory, Vygotsky emphasized that the development of the psyche of children and adolescents occurs through society and social interaction. Therefore, mental development is carried out under the influence of great obstacles and pressure on young people.

2. The social nature of thinking. According to Vygotsky, the process of human thinking develops through social relations. During adolescence, children and adolescents go through new stages of restoring their abilities and realizing their personality. During this period, "social crises" occur.

3. Intellectual crises. Vygotsky believes that the mental development of young people is associated with the improvement of processes related to synthesis and analysis, clarity of thinking and reasoning. During this period, it is necessary to deepen thinking and social imagination in the process of mental work. One of their most important crises is the new formation of "pleasure" or "a sense of oneself or one's rightness".

4. Overcoming the crisis: according to Vygotsky, crises of mental development are of great importance because they serve the development of new intellectual capabilities of a person. The goal is to achieve spiritual and intellectual progress through these processes.

For Vygotsky, adolescent crises are an important part of life, not only personal, but also social.

After the primary school period, the child goes through two stages in the process of forming his attitude towards himself as a separate person. These stages divide adolescence into two separate periods - the early adolescence and the late adolescence. In the first stage, the teenager wants to separate himself from the "children" and emphasize that he now belongs to the adult world. Interest in adult life is the main characteristic of teenagers.

This period is characterized by imitation of the behavior of adults and the inability to critically evaluate his inadequate actions, his closeness to adults, excessive dependence on a group of peers who help him, and similar situations. In the second stage, the teenager no longer doubts that he is not a young child, and begins to clearly realize his personality, glorify his personality, and begin to perform unique actions. Teenagers are more interested in thoughts about their personality, they try to know themselves, purposefully develop and educate themselves.

During adolescence, great qualitative changes occur in the growth of internal freedom, self-awareness and independent behavior. Will is also important in the emergence of such changes. As a higher mental function, will is considered an instrument of free movement of a teenager, as well as the main line of personality development. By this time, his actions no longer depend on the group of peers with whom he is friends.

Even when friends try to make a teenager think seriously and turn away from false ideas about himself, he can easily refuse and firmly stand his ground. During this period, with excessive interest, examining the inner world of other people and analyzing one's own behavior, the emergence of elements of self-education are characteristic features of the life of adolescents at this second stage. Adolescence is often characterized by such negative characteristics as reluctance, stubbornness, obstinacy, failure to recognize one's own shortcomings, belligerence.

Teenagers see the independence and freedom of adults in life, on the screen and in books, their own great and

they see and envy their interesting work, bold actions, heroism, reputation among others.

A teenager has an interest and desire to be an adult or at least seem like an adult, and it seems easy for him to realize this desire. The discrepancy between the needs and capabilities of adolescents gives rise to conflicts between adolescents and their parents, teachers and other mentors. The teenager strives to fulfill his numerous "I want" desires: to use everything that adults have, to be free, independent and free.

CONCLUSION

Thus, Vygotsky experimentally proved that children's egocentric speech does not originate from inclinations and children's fantasy that are far from reality. He is the organizer of practical actions. Thinking to himself, the child plans an action. In "Thinking and Speech" (1934), Vygotsky studied the development of concepts in children based on experimental research. According to Vygotsky, only education that precedes development yields good results. The term "coastal development zone" is introduced. This concept implies a gap between the levels of tasks that a child can solve independently under the guidance of adults. Learning creates such a zone and leads to development.

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